

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15363654

Workforce Diversity and Organizational Performance in Federal Universities in South East

¹Ejiofor Ngozi Ukamaka; ²Oderah Okeke Ph.D; ³Uju Muogbo Ph.D & ⁴Chioma Keyna Ozurumba

^{1,4}**Business administration department
Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ikwo, Ebonyi State, Nigeria**

^{2,3}**Department of Business Administration,
Faculty of Management Sciences,
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of workforce diversity and organizational performance in federal universities in southeast. The problems of this study was the discriminatory attitude of some workforce, individual identity, lack of cooperation amongst workers has been extended by workers in same diverse organization beyond limits, which dampens morale with negative performance index. The study examined work diversity and organizational performance in federal universities in South East. Specifically, the study determined the effect of age diversity on organizational performance of federal universities in southeast, Nigeria. Ascertain the effect of gender diversity on organizational performance of federal universities in southeast, Nigeria. Examine the effect of ethnic diversity on organizational performance of federal universities in southeast, Nigeria. Determine the effect of educational diversity on organizational performance of federal universities in southeast, Nigeria. This work is anchored on the Social Identity Theory (SIT). The study adopted survey method of research. The hypotheses were tested using regression analysis method at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed, Age diversity has no significant effect on organizational performance of federal universities in South East Nigeria. T-statistics of 1.051 and probability value of 1.012. Gender diversity has significant effect on organizational performance of federal universities in South East Nigeria. T-statistics of 2.014 and probability value of 000. Ethnic diversity has significant effect on organizational performance of teaching hospitals in South East Nigeria. T-statistics of 2.112 and probability value of 0.000. The study recommends that For firms to foster and promote workforce innovativeness, other things being equal, they need to adopt the culture of recruiting work-teams characterized with ethnicity diversity, to enhance idea generation, idea exploration, fine-tuning and implementation. Firms need to some level of age diversity within their workforce to ensure that the proper balance is created to enhance their proper adaptation to changes. This study also recommends that

Keywords: Workforce Diversity, Federal Universities South East

INTRODUCTION

Diversity in the workplace is increasing all over the world. Diversity within the workplace is vital for the organization. To become competitive in the market place, the business organization must hire the

competent workforce. The inclusion of employees of different categories will add value to the existing knowledge and practice (Kundu & Mor, 2017). In today's scenario, workforce diversity is essential for the economic and intellectual development of the organization (Saxena, 2014). Workforce diversity is critical for organizational success and makes the organization strive more toward the organizational goals and objectives (Anthony, 2014). An organization that has a diverse workforce are likely to perform better than the organizations without diversity (Sikailieh & Mkoji, 2012).

In Nigeria, workplace diversity has been widely attributed to the demographic composition of a workforce, whether in the private or public sector. In empirical studies, diversity is usually measured using the compositional approach, otherwise known as Surface-level or demographic diversity, which refers to the extent to which a unit is heterogeneous on characteristics such as gender, ethnicity, religion, age, functional background, and organizational tenure (Tsui and Gutek, 2010). Contemporary believe system is marked by a generalized sense that traditional work arrangements are inadequate to address the challenges organizations encounter in recent times. The new complexity of work operations demands more diverse functions and the use of more diverse talents. As the need for employee diversity increases, so do demands like the need for effective interaction among diverse employees, the potential for conflict among them and the urgency to manage this conflicts in order to attain the organizational objectives (Schneider and Northcraft, 2019).

In the past twenty years, the growing diverse work force in organizations has led scholars to pay increased attention to the issue of workforce diversity (Gupta, 2013). Business organizations in the developed and developing countries are all caught up in the globalization web, which has heralded increased demographic and socio-cultural diversity in the workforce. In the light of this reality, the recognition of workforce diversity as a source of competitive advantage has become a reality in organizations today and has generated an enormous amount of interest over the recent years among business leaders, governments and within the civil society (Kochan, Ely, Joshi & Thomas, 2012). Companies are recognizing the need to leverage their diversity in the context of globalization to maintain a competitive edge in the marketplace (Richard, 2019). Childs (2015) argues that any business that intends to be successful must have a borderless view of the workforce by ensuring that workforce diversity is part of its day to day business conduct. Today's workforce is getting more and more heterogeneous due to the effects of globalization (Kurtulus, 2012). When workforce diversity is not managed properly, there will be a potential for higher voluntary employee turnover, difficulty in communication and destructive interpersonal conflicts (Elsaid, 2012). The reverse leads to a more engaged workforce and subsequently improved organizational performance (Gitonga, Kamaara & Orwar, 2016).

Diversity can generally be defined as recognizing, understanding and accepting individual differences irrespective of their race, gender, age, class, ethnicity, physical ability, sexual orientation, spiritual practice and so on (Dike, 2013). Grobler (2012) also supports this view by adding that each individual is unique but also shares any number of environmental or biological characteristics. Nigeria, like many nations of the world, is ethnically heterogeneous, and is characterized by other demographic diversities, which are reflective in the Workforce. This phenomenon is one of the most challenging human resource and organizational issues of our time (Ogbo, Kifordu & Wilfred, 2014). Academicians and practitioners have sought to understand the impact of diversity and its management on organizational effectiveness (Afolabi & Omole, 2011). The difficulties and challenges of managing workforce diversity in Nigeria have taken some tolls on most business organizations in the country. It is against these backdrops that this study x-rays the effect of workforce diversity on organizational performance of federal Universities in southeast, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Today's workforce is getting more and more heterogeneous due to the effects of globalization (Kurtulus, 2012). Elsaid (2012) and Aghazadeh (2014) observed that when workforce diversity is not managed properly, it will consequently lead to high rate of labour turnover, difficulty in communication, low productivity, destructive interpersonal conflicts, high level of inefficiencies and ineffectiveness. Workforce diversity can be an important instrument for firms to not only enhance their organizational performance but to be able to attain a competitive edge against its

business rivals in the business market and attain sustainability. In recent years, Diversity Management and workforce diversity have been substantial and as such have forced companies to embrace these concepts in their companies with the aim of increasing productivity and profit. This forced integration has created divergence and uncertainty in the workforce, as management is not skilled enough to control the concept of diversity management and its ethics, and so managers are finding it difficult to effectively practice diversity management, which in turn has become an albatross on their neck.

When left un-managed, employee diversity is more likely to damage morale, increase employee turnover, and cause significant communication problems (Jehn, Northcraft, & Neale, 1999). The most important issues of workforce diversity are to address the problems of discrimination in terms of gender, age, ethnicity, education background and culture. The discriminatory attitude of some workforce, individual identity, lack of cooperation amongst workers has been extended by workers in same diverse organization beyond limits, which dampens morale with negative performance index. This is because departmental goals are pursued more at the expense of broad organizational goals and objectives. Corporate profitability dwindles because the core values of diversity are not properly harnessed (Salami, 2010). It is against this backdrop that the study seeks to examine the effect of workforce diversity and organizational performance in federal universities in southeast, Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Workforce Diversity

The term diversity means being different in cultural, belief, value, religion, inspiration, perspiration and more. It is a fact of life which is natural and irreversible and the same time makes life beautiful, attractive, interesting, and less monotonous (Mujtaba, 2017). Bartz, Hillman, Lehrer, and Mayhugh (2010) opined that the diversity in workplace could be seen in various elements such as difference in race, gender, age, and ethnicity. The authors observed that workforce diversity has been an area of critical attention by human resource management who advocates for the quality of workforce diversity to be achieved via proper management in order to enhanced productivity. Instances of workforce diversity are observed in factors such as culture, gender, age, a disability, and experience. Diversity may also present in terms of as a single parent, liberal or conservative point of view, and work style (Hanamura, 2019).

Managing diversity means striving to develop an organizational culture that is heterogeneous and maximize the involvement of all individuals to their full capacities (Thomas, 2016). Age, gender, race, education, religion, and culture are all factors that might impact a task or relationship inside an organization, according to Carrell (2016). To understand the impact of workforce diversity, Skaggs and DiTomaso (2014) argue that one must consider the implications of the distribution of valuable and scarce resources, interpersonal interactions, and the compositional influences of the unit such as job, vocation, organization, or society. Bahamon (2012) noted that conducive work climate has been known to drive of performance and add greatly to organizational results. The concern for provision of work climate anchors independently on the management team of an organization whose behavior determines the work climate. A positive behaviour influences the work climate which enhances motivation and the aroused motivation for work as a result of the managements' ability to coordinate employees' diversity at work. Further, Luring (2011) noted that workforce becomes more global and progressively more culturally diverse, it becomes a challenge for communication to pass smoothly more effectively either by group-based or individual-based.

In other words, diverse workplace makes it impossible for employees to correlate and associate with each other for the benefit of the concerned organization and the individual workers concerned as well. Mulkeen (2018) explained workplace diversity as all the differences in age, gender, sexual orientation, educational background, cultural framework, religiosity, and life experience. The same author added that today's workforce does not exist in isolation but takes part of an emerging international business atmosphere where effective business communication is essential for sustainable organizational growth. Similarly, Hunt (2011) opined that workplaces are the only angle at which individuals from diverse cultures convene and engage in collaborations which renews and broadens the essence of an organization. Okoro and

Washington (2012) noted that most studies opined that workforce diversity in the 21st century is attributed to globalization which has contributed to the ease movement of people from one place to another.

Age Diversity

Age refers to the different stages in one's life cycle. Age diversity is the ability to accept all different types of ages within a business environment. Companies have to adjust to an aging population in various ways. Age diversity offers positive advantages for healthy organizations, just like any other sort of diversity in work and life. Treating people fairly, regardless of age, is central to the principles of ethical business and ethical organizations. Robbins & Judge (2013) said the relationship between age and workers job performance is likely to be a subject of increasing significance during the next decade. According to them, the reasons for this are; first, place of work is characterized by aging population. As such, quite a number of employers know that older employees signify a huge potential pool of high excellence applicants. Thirdly, is the system set by some countries that outlaw compulsory retirement e.g. the USA. It is a common to presume that as people get older, their skills in terms of nimbleness, strength, speed and harmonization begins to turn down and job could become boring and lack of intellectual inspiration all contributes to abridged productivity.

Researchers (Truxitlo, Cadiz, and Rineer, 2015) have studied ageing and age diversity in the workforce from number of disciplines, theoretical perspectives and level of analysis. Much theoretical and empirical work has shed light on age- related change at work- whether that involves abilities, cognitive abilities (Cattell, 2011), personality, work motivation or employees work attitudes and performance (Ng & Feedman, 2010). Lange (2016) cited that ageing is a multidimensional process. He focused on the different meanings of age and ageing, going beyond chronological age to highlighting the role of age perception subjective age, relative age, psychological age) in shaping individual attitudes and behavior. We need to reconceptualize age if we want to change the way we manage age diversity. European commission (2014) underlined the need to support the mature workforce by promoting active ageing policies that target better working condition that value an older and most skilled workforce.

Gender Diversity

Man's and woman's different experiences may provide insights into the man and woman may have different cognitive abilities such as man's proficiency in mathematics and woman's proficiency in verbal and interpersonal skills (Hoffman 2015; Maccoby and Jacklin 2014). An assortment of different cognitive abilities in a team with positive gender diversity can magnify the overall creativity and innovation. Messick and Mackic (2019) noted the categorization based on race, gender, and age is common. A gender diverse work group may produce the psychological groups of male group members and female group members; subsequently the social comparison between male and female psychological groups triggers in group out group dynamics, as a result, gender diversity may produce negative group behavior such as decreased communication (Kravitz, 2013), role expectation base on stereotypes (Elsaas and Graves, 2017), reduction in team cohesiveness (Triandis, Kurowski and Gelfand, 2014) in team collaboration (Chatman and Flynn 2001) and increased group conflict (Pelled, 2016).

Gender refers to the socially constructed roles for women, girls, men and boys. Gender roles are learned, changeable over time, and variable within and between cultures. Gender often defines the duties, responsibilities, constraints, opportunities and privileges of women, girls, men and boys in any context. Gender equality refers to the equal enjoyment of their rights, responsibilities and opportunities and it implies that the interests, needs and priorities of each gender are respected. Gender diversity is an umbrella term that is used to describe gender identities that demonstrate a diversity of expression beyond the binary framework. For many gender diverse people, the concept of binary gender – having to choose to express yourself as male or female – is constraining. Some people would prefer to have the freedom to change from one gender to another, or not have a gender identity at all. Others just want to be able to openly defy or challenge more normalized concepts of gender. For gender diverse people, their identity is about presenting something more outwardly authentic to the world; whether they understand themselves to be differently gendered, or have no gender at all

Ethnic Diversity

Ethnicity is identity related to a specific cultural or national tradition. Ethnic diversity, then, refers to the presence of different ethnic backgrounds or identities. In the United States, many people identify with more than one ethnic group, and they might experience ethnic diversity within their own families. It is vital to look closely to how persons and different groups within the working surroundings interact with each other at work as organizations are becoming more varied in its ethnicity (Weiliang, Mun, Fong, & Yuan, 2014). It is necessary for managers to have information on diversity and ways in which they can manage ethnic variety of their labor force in ways that will help the organization take full advantage of the beneficial aspect of ethnic diversity while plummeting the negative effects that could sprout out in form of conflict or communication issues (Benschop, 2011). According to the social identity, social categorization and similarity magnetism theories, when a labor force is ethnically diverse, it could result in psychological processes like in-group liking, in-group magnetism and worst of all in-group favoritism. The outcome of this may affect the behaviours of workers in a way that group members may only decide to favour those belonging to their ethnic background. This could also bring about a lot of negative outcomes like; less message, less cooperation, less cohesiveness and even conflicts.

Furthermore, it could lead to high turnover intension and less job satisfaction (Oerlemans, Peeters, & Schaufeli, 2013). Ethnicity is a surface level characteristics (Jackson, Et al, 2015) and it can be quickly used to divide a group of people into ethnic sub- groups. People may frequently identify with their ethnic background because it provides them with the sense of belongingness, it connects individuals to a group of closely related people who share a common culture (Cashmore, 2016 & Smith, 2011). A theoretical paradigm which may explain consequences of ethnic diversity is the similarity attraction paradigm of Byrne (2011). This paradigm states that a great variety of physical, social or other attributes can be used as a basis for expecting similarity in attitudes, beliefs or personality. The increase in ethnic diversity along with accompanying demographic developments, have had a significant impact on the composition of the workforce (Ekampen and Wetters, 2015). About 50 years ago the demographic features of most work organization were fairly homogeneous (Willians and Reilly, 2018). Many employees shared a similar ethnic background, were male and worked for the same employers throughout their working lives (Peeters, 2019). Nowadays, managers are confronted with teams and departments that are more diverse in terms of gender, age, and ethnicity and so on (Schaufeli, 2019).

Educational Diversity

Cohen & Bailey (2015) said differences in the educational setting of workers can bring about important effect on group performance just like their diverse capabilities since it promotes a wide variety of talents. Holland (2017) mentioned that a person's favorite of a certain field of knowledge can, in some ways disclose the character and the strong point of such individual. This entails that the background education of a person point out the competences of the individual. As such, managers welcome individuals with different educational background as a way of encouraging the labor force to successfully work with each other in order to accomplish organization's goals (Gwendolyn, 2012). For example, a computer scientist is often predictable to possess information that is different from that of a marketer (Hambrick & Mason, 2012). When an organization has a labor force that has different educational background, it is likely to enlarge the variety of its information base revealing the diverse educational background of its workers (Cohen & Levinthal, 2014).

Cultural Diversity

Baridam and Nwibere (2018) are of the opinion that an organizations culture is a hidden but unifying force that provides meaning and direction in the organization. The culture of a workplace may be a very important consideration for effective diversity management as diversity and diversity management practices have become more prevalent in workplaces across the globe. Effective diversity management is even more important for a culturally diverse nation like Nigeria and some Multinational Companies (MNCs) which not only have to manage the diversity of their workforce across geographic regions, but also do so with consideration for the history and traditions that are unique to each country within their corporate umbrella. According to Aluko (2013), culture is a wide and multidimensional concept that one cannot hope to deal with in its entirety in a single study. This is because culture is divided into two major

aspects which are (i) material and (ii) non-material cultures. Aluko (2013) goes further to describe material culture as the physical pieces that are clear and noticeable, such as clothing, tools, technology and art. The non-material aspects of culture are described as the abstract ideas and ways of thinking, morals, languages, attitudes, values, and norms shared and transmitted in a society. They cannot be seen or touched but can be revealed through the psychological state and behavior of individuals.

Differences in cultural characteristics can predict team scores which can further be interpreted as an advantage of having ethnically different views for a team, resulting in increased problem solving and team performance. Many private firms have also manifested this kind of diversity, although a good number- especially the multinationals and those that have adopted professionalism as a value hire purely on merit (Zgourides & Watson, 2012). While there have been a significant number of studies that have explored the effect of diversity at individual and group level, there is little theoretical guidance and a scarcity of empirical findings concerning the potentially beneficial impact of firm-level cultural diversity on organizational outcomes (Richard Dwyer & Chadwick, 2003). Researchers have observed that diversity on a cultural context can influence organizational synergies, innovativeness, and effectiveness in implementation of technological programs (Gomez-Mejia & Palich, 2015).

Cultural diversity can further influence interpersonal dynamics within an organization. Interpersonal barriers rooted in cultural differences may impede the flow of information on a corporate wide basis. Cultural norms and practices may further influence the manner in which human resource programs are implemented (Gomez-Mejia *et al.*, 2015). Culture is critical to business success, according to the results of the 2013 Culture and Change Management Survey. When more than 2,200 global businesspeople were surveyed to get their take on culture's role in business, it was observed that culture is widely seen as more important than companies' strategies or operating models. This view of culture's importance holds true around the world (Gilbert & Ivancevich, 2010). According to Ahiauzu (2019), cultural diversity implies diversity in religion, norms, values and attitude. The growth of cultural diversity was the focus since before Christ was born. To achieve organizational goals, the management needs to manage employees with different cultural diversity. When people of diverse cultures are grouped together to perform a specific task, it will lead to high effectiveness and efficiency of the organization. Multicultural workforce is an influential source of heterogeneity which can be positive on efficiency and effectiveness. This is as a result of different people pooling their belief, knowledge and skills together to achieve effective productivity in the organization.

Organizational Performance

Organizational performance comprises the actual output or results of an organization as measured against its intended outputs (or goals and objectives). According to Richard *et al.* (2019), organizational performance encompasses three specific areas of firm outcomes: (a) financial performance (profits, return on assets, return on investment, etc.); (b) product market performance (sales, market share, etc.); and (c) shareholder return (total shareholder return, economic value added, etc). Organizational performance is the ultimate dependent variable of interest for researchers concerned with just about any area of management (Devinney *et al.*, 2010). This broad construct is essential in allowing researchers and managers to evaluate firms over time and compare them to rivals. In short, organizational performance is the most important criterion in evaluating organizations, their actions, and environments. Performance of an employee at his/her workplace is a point of concern for all the organizations irrespective of all the factors and conditions. Consequently the employees are considered to be very important asset for their organizations. (Qureshi & Ramay, 2016) A good performance of the employees of an organization leads towards a good organizational performance thus ultimately making an organization more successful and effective and the vice versa. (Armstrong & Baron, 2018). These moderators were further investigated and strong correlations between organizational commitment and work behavior were found against self reported and for supervisory report of performance. The problems arise for the organizations when they start perceiving that their organizations are already performing at their level best and with great efficiency furthermore, there is no need for further improvement in their organizations (Summers & Hyman, 2015). Hence keeping in view these barriers must be tackled and addressed as they result in underdeveloped competencies and more over lead towards, finally the organizational ineffectiveness. Ultimate success or

failure of an organization is determined majorly by the performance of their employees. (Bartlett & Ghoshal, 2015).

Theoretical Framework

This work is anchored on the Social Identity Theory (SIT), which states that individuals experience collective identity based on their membership in a group, such as racial/ethnic and gender identities. To understand the relationship between workforce diversity and the organizational performance, various researchers have gone into the in-depth study of the phenomenon, and come up with varied theories that can be used to better understand it. First of the theories is the Social Identity Theory (SIT), this theory was initially formulated by Tajfel and Turner (1979) in the 1970s and 80s. The theory helps to shed more light on workforce diversity and organizational performance (Turner and Reynolds 2010). The social identity theory is known as a means of predicting workplace and societal inter-group behavior. The social identity theory is recognized as a helping hand to better understand the fashion in which people in social groups interact, which predicts that they carry out their different roles on the basis of a preexisting stereotype, differences in status, individual status, legitimacy and stability of such differences. The theory is also believed to predict inter-group behavior based on the perceived abilities of persons in the group to transit from one group to another.

The structure of the social identity theory provides an image into individual persons' cognizance of each other's social identity and individual behavior at their workplace. The theory as well, predicts the weight of individual identity within an organization and its social structures. Secondly, Buunk and Gibbons (2007) ascertain the essential element of the social identity theory with its divisions, group contact and comparison in individual's awareness of the self and others. Their argument draws on the part of social perception in the context of individual differences based on their ethnic background, gender, education/profession, religion, and work experience, type of work and duty locations among others. The effective management of the difference in these individualities will apparently be important for the performance of organizations. According to Abrams & Hogg (1990), there are numerous units that are very important to better understand the linkage between workplace diversity and service quality, efficiency and effectiveness in the organization. This study seeks to confirm the existence and the impacts of workforce diversity and its contribution to increased organizational performance

Empirical Review

Okilo Kakatei Tubonimi & Bariweni (2023) identify the relationship between workplace diversity management and organizational performance. The study is a review of extant literature on the relationship between workplace diversity management and organizational performance. The result of the study shows that workplace diversity is strongly related to organisational performance. Therefore, workplace diversity is an important and inevitable factor in organisations due to the rapid economic growth and advancement, which requires that firms become more diversified, particularly in multiracial and multi-ethnic countries. The study recommends that business organisations should continue to adopt workplace diversity as a veritable tool for enhancing performance. Organisations should embrace workplace diversity to achieve market performance, innovative performance, and stakeholder performance

Tamunomiebi, & Onyeché, (2021) examined the relationship between diversity management and organizational performance of 3-star hotels in South-South, Nigeria. The study categorized diversity management into surface-level diversity and deep-level diversity and investigated these two dimensions. The target population of the study consisted of all the 3-star hotels in South-South Nigeria registered with the Nigeria Tourism Development Corporation given as 60 hotels. The sample frame consisted of the managerial/ administrative staff of the hotels and five of them were selected from each of the 60 hotels in the South-South giving a total of 300 managers. The data for the study were generated using structured questionnaire. Also, the hypotheses were tested using use of inferential statistical tools of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) and t-test through the help of SPSS 22.0. The study found that understanding and managing diversity plays a significant role in enhancing organisational performance. The study concluded that surface-level diversity has a positive and significant relationship with the

productivity of 3-star hotels in South-South, Nigeria; deep-level diversity has a positive and significant relationship with the productivity of 3-star hotels in South-South, Nigeria; surface-level diversity has a positive and significant relationship with the growth of 3-star hotels in South-South, Nigeria; and deep-level diversity has a positive and significant relationship with the growth of 3-star hotels in South-South, Nigeria. Therefore, the study recommended that it is important that effective workplace strategies and policies be designed, implemented and monitored, in order not only to eliminate discrimination but also to support a more diverse workforce.

Kifordu, & Ezeonwumelu, (2023) investigate the effect of diversity management on the performance of employees in selected banks across Delta State. The study was anchored on social identity theory of exclusion in the workplace. A descriptive survey research design was used for the study. Data was sourced using the primary source. A population of 900 employees from selected banks in Delta State was used for the study. A sample size of 173 employees derived through Borg and Gall was used for the study. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire. The instrument was subjected to both face and content validity. A reliability co-efficient of 0.79 was obtained through the test-retest method. The data collected was analyzed using frequency count and percentages while ANOVA was used to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that gender, age, ethnicity, and educational diversity had significant positive effects on employees' performance. The study recommended that in setting up teams in the workplace, personnel department in line with top managers must ensure that there is a proper representation of members of various ethnic groups, age and gender so as to create room for effective succession planning. Management should choose the most qualified in terms of academics to ensure that appropriate guides to thinking are done to formulate policies on diversity management and firm performance.

Ugwuzor, (2014) examined the nature of the relationship between Workforce Diversity Management and Corporate Performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Despite efforts aimed at optimizing the performance of firms in Nigeria, a nation of many diverse people, not much appears to have been achieved. To address this lacuna, primary data was collected from Forty-two registered firms in South-South Nigeria using a five-point Likert-type scale questionnaire and personal interviews. The Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient at 95% confidence level and the Hierarchical Multiple Regression model were used to analyse the data. The findings revealed that the apparent low performance rate of the Study firms may be traceable to poor management of surface and deep level diversity. To optimize Corporate Performance therefore, it was recommended that managers should ensure that employees are "not at all" disturbed by issues bothering on diversity.

Olusoji, (2023) examined how diversity in the workplace influences satisfaction of employees of tertiary institutions in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. Survey research design was used and a sample of three hundred and eighty-nine (389) respondents were obtained from the total population of thirteen thousand, eight hundred and twenty-two (13,822) employees in six (6) Nigerian tertiary institutions. Data obtained in the survey were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical tools (such as frequency count, simple percentage, and mean, standard deviation, and Karl Pearson correlation). In specific, the Karl Pearson correlation results indicated that while diversity dimensions of gender and age had insignificant influence on employees' satisfaction, it was found that ethnicity and education had significant influence on employees' satisfaction in Nigerian tertiary institutions. In view of the findings, it was recommended that management of tertiary institutions should consider workplace diversity (workforce educational level and ethnic groups) as a vital factor when formulating policy frameworks. In addition, there is the need for management of tertiary institutions to incessantly take proactive measures aimed at managing diversity elements such as age and gender in order to attain the desired satisfaction by the workforce. This study contributes to the human resource management literature by revealing that employees' satisfaction is driven not by age and gender, but as a result of educational qualification and tribal sentiments

Dhruba & Nischal (2023) examined the effect of work force diversity factors (generational diversity, gender diversity, ethnic/racial diversity) and the role of managerial expertise on organizational performance. This study followed the correlational research design as it intends to evaluate the impact of workforce diversity on banking sector performance. The population of the study was managerial level

employees working in banking sector of Nepal and 156 responses were collected and analyzed. Five-point Likert scale questionnaire was used to collect the data. Correlation matrix and regression model were used to analyses the data. Physical diversity characters; age, gender and ethnicity were considered for the study. Research concluded that gender and ethnic diversity positively affect the organizational performance but age diversity may cause conflict in the organization, however, managerial expertise positively affect organization performance which can contribute to reduce conflict that arise because of age diversity in the organization

Okeke, & Mbah (2023) examined the effect of diversity management on organizational performance by using the Federal tertiary health institutions in the South-East, Nigeria as the study area. The dimensions of diversity identified for the study functional expertise, experience and work experience diversity. The design adopted for the study was descriptive survey design. From a population of 1,971 from the selected institutions in the study, a sample of 379 was determined through the application of Borg and Gall Statistical formula for determining sample size from a finite population. Major statistical tools of analysis in the study were Karl Pearson Correlation Coefficient and multiple regression analysis. All tests were conducted at 0.05 level of significance. Major findings from the study held that, functional expertise, experience and diversity had significant positive effect on organizational performance. However, gender, functional expertise and organizational experience predicted organizational performance more than other diversity dimensions. The study concluded that effective management of employees 'diversity leads to enhanced organizational performance. It was recommended among others that organizations should deliberately make diversity policy to facilitate its effective management for better outcomes.

Usulor Afuecheta, & Igbokwe, (2023) investigate the impact of genuine commitment to workforce diversity management on employees' performance in Nigerian public institutions; and to examine the effects of organizations' perception and interpretation of diversity on employees' performance. The study is anchored on resource-based, and core competencies theories. The study adopted descriptive survey using questionnaire to elicit information from respondents purposively selected from Nigerian public institutions. Findings of the study include; lack of genuine commitment to diversity management impacts negatively on employees' performance; wrong perception and interpretation of workplace diversity affects employees' performance. The study therefore recommend among others; understanding the fundamental differences among workers of Nigeria public institutions; effective workforce diversity management as an organization with such strategy will have a leading edge in employee productivity and retention

Mihretu.Kenenisa and Chalchissa (2023). explore the degree of association between workforce diversity dimensions and academic performance of four universities in Ethiopia. The diversity management attributes assessed were diversity Climate, values and organizational justice; and identity, schemas and communication with adaptation to the contexts of the higher education institutions in Ethiopia. The Full account of these diversity management dimensions is presented in detail in the methodology section of this paper. The sample universities were selected purposively, and stratified and systematic sampling techniques were further used to identify respondents. The number of respondents that took part in the study was 386. Quantitative and qualitative data were collected to test the various study hypotheses. Descriptive statistics and simple correlation analyses were used to analyze the data. The demographic features of the staff working in the four case study universities was found to be diverse with regard to gender, marital status, age and religion. The agreement level of the staff with regard to the prevalence of diversity management dimension in their university was found to above the ideal average. The mean values of the Likert scale response ranged from 3.72 (with standard deviation of 0.98) for 'organizational justice' to 4.12 (with standard deviation of 0.74) for diversity management dimension designated as 'values.' Results from Pearson correlation analysis revealed that there are statistically significant positive correlations between the dimensions of workforce diversity and organizational performance. This implies that organizational performance of higher education institutions can be significantly and positively influenced by extant diversity. The practical implication of this is that attention needs to be given to the fair distribution of resources to the teaching staff working in these universities in the future. The freedom to express one's own identity in the university workforce landscape was also observed to be limited in the universities studied and this has to be also improved.

Gap in Literature

Majority of the empirical studies reviewed such as Walid and Zubair (2016) carried out a study on impact of effective teamwork on employee performance, using the entertainment company in Kuala Lumpur capital of Malaysia, as the study area. Result from data analysis indicates that significant relationship exist between teamwork and employee performance. It was concluded that the current team building in the plant should be sustained. Ooko (2013) did a study on impact of teamwork on the achievement of targets in organizations in Kenya, using SOS children’s village, Eldoret was the study area. It was concluded that there was no effective teamwork at SOS despite employees being aware of how much they can achieve by working together in teams. Salamatu (2014) studied the role of team building on employee performance. It was found that team building focuses on and integrates harmonization and this helped in increased service delivery of a firm. Mba (2012) carried out a survey study on teamwork and employee performance in the Bonny Nigeria Liquefied Natural Gas Plant Port Harcourt. The study concluded that teamwork influences employee performance especially in service delivery. Oni and Daniya (2013) conducted a survey study on the impact of empowerment and teambuilding on employee service delivery: From the findings of the study, it was concluded that teambuilding brings about empowerment, thereby increasing employee service delivery

From the analysis above, it is evident that there is gap in literature from various findings from different authors; this is from the method of analysis used, model adopted and geographical location. This study will complement the existing literature by using regression analysis and ANOVA Method of analysis to examine the true situation of effect of workforce diversity and organizational performance in federal universities in southeast, Secondly, the study will choose federal universities in southeast because no study has taken consideration in that aspect.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In this study, descriptive survey research design was adopted since the unit of analysis was based on more than one Firm, The descriptive statistics and Multiple Regression Analysis used to analyze the data.

Data Analysis

Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression result was employed to test the effect of independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variables. The result of the multiple regression analysis is presented in the tables below.

Table 1 Summary of the Regression Result

The result of the multiple regressions formulated in chapter three is presented in the tables below.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.698 _a	.587	.579	1.10305	.487	64.704	5	341	.000	1.920

a. Predictors: (Constant), AGD, GDD, ETD, EDD

b. Dependent Variable: ORP

Table 3 shows that R² which measures the strength of the effect of independent variable on the dependent variable have the value of 59%. This implies that 21% of the variation in diversity management is explained by variations in age, gender, ethnic, educational and cultural diversity. This was supported by adjusted R² of 58%.

In order to check for autocorrelation in the model, Durbin-Watson statistics was employed. Durbin-Watson statistics of 1.920 in table 3 shows that the variables in the model are not auto correlated and that the model is reliable for predications.

Table 2: ANOVA Result

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	393.637	5	78.727	64.704	.000 ^b
	Residual	414.905	341	1.217		
	Total	808.542	346			

a. Dependent Variable: ORP

b. Predictors: (Constant), AGD, GDD, ETD, EDD,

The f-statistics value of 64.704 in table 3 with f-statistics probability of 0.000 shows that the independent variables has significant effect on dependent variables that is, age, gender, ethnic, educational and cultural diversity, can collectively explain the variations in workforce diversity and organizational performance.

Table 3 Coefficients of the Model

T-statistics and probability value from the regression result are the effect of individual independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variables. The summary of the result is presented in the table below.

Table 3 T-Statistics and Probability Value from the Regression Result

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	.311	.121		8.632	.060	-.990	.020
	AGD	.074	.059	.083	1.051	.012	.430	.623
	GDD	.159	.053	.194	2.014	.000	.491	.711
	ETD	.091	.054	.128	2.112	.001	-.014	.219
	EDD	.110	.052	.140	3.004	.000	-.031	.200

a. Dependent Variable: ORP

Source: Author's Compilation from SPSS Version 21.0

Table 3 shows the coefficient of the individual variables and their probability values. Age diversity variables have regression t-value of 0.074with a probability value of .1.051. This implies that age diversity have a positive but insignificant effect on organizational performance. Gender diversity has a regression t-test of 2.014 with a probability value of 0.000 implying that gender diversity s has a positive and insignificant effect on organizational performance.

On a similar note, ethnic diversity has a t-test value of 2.112 and a probability value of 0001. This shows that ethnic diversity has a positive and significant effect on organizational performance.

Furthermore, educational diversity has a regression coefficient of 3.004 with a probability value of 0.000. This implies that educational diversity has a positive and significant effect on organizational performance

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

HO: Age diversity has no significant impact on organizational performance of federal universities in southeast, Nigeria

Age diversity has a t-statistics of 1.051 and a probability value of 0.012 which is statistically insignificant. Therefore, we reject the alternative hypothesis and accept the null hypotheses which state that age diversity has no significant impact on organizational performance of federal universities in southeast, Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Two

HO₁: Gender diversity has no significant impact on organizational performance of federal universities in southeast, Nigeria.

In testing this hypothesis, the t-statistics and probability value in table above is used. Gender diversity has a t-statistics of 2.014 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the alternative hypothesis and accept the null hypotheses which state that gender diversity has a significant impact on organizational performance of federal universities in southeast, Nigeria

Test of Hypothesis Three

HO₃: Ethnic diversity has no significant impact on organizational performance of federal universities in southeast, Nigeria

Ethnic diversity has a t-statistics of 2.112 and a probability value of 0.001 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that ethnic diversity has a significant impact on organizational performance of Federal Universities in Southeast, Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Four

HO: Educational diversity has no significant impact on affect organizational performance of Federal Universities in Southeast, Nigeria

Educational diversity has a t-statistics of 3.004 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses and conclude that educational diversity has a significant impact on affect organizational performance of Federal Universities in southeast, Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Workforce diversity has been identified to lead to improved organizational performance as a result of the broad based nature and the specialization it brings on board. It was on this premise that this study did set out to conceptualize and empirically investigate the workforce diversity and organizational performance in federal universities in southeast, Nigeria as a case study. The findings of the study reveal that apart from age diversity, other dimensions of workforce diversity used in this research (such as gender, ethnic, educational and cultural diversity) do have positive relationship with the organizational performance of firms. Based on these findings, the study therefore concludes that workforce diversity when properly managed has a significant positive effect on organizational performance of firms.

RECOMMENDATION

Amongst the recommendation is that the federal Universities to foster and promote workforce innovativeness, other things being equal, they need to adopt the culture of recruiting work-teams characterized with ethnicity diversity, to enhance idea generation, idea exploration, fine-tuning and implementation. Federal Universities need to some level of age diversity within their workforce to ensure that the proper balance is created to enhance their proper adaptation to changes. This study therefore recommends that Federal Universities should formulate policies that guide against gender discrimination in their Universities in other to encourage innovative and creativity. In setting up teams in the workplace, personnel department in line with top managers must ensure that there is a proper representation of members of various ethnic groups, age and gender so as to create room for effective succession planning and integration

REFERENCES

Afolabi, O. A., & Omole, E. O. (2011). Personality type and workforce diversity as predictors of ethical behaviour & job satisfaction among Nigerian policemen. *Current Research Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(14), 381-388.

- Agbaeze, E.K. Nkwonta N. C. and Obiefuna, C. E. (2019) Effect of workforce diversity on performance of manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research* 27 (5): 400-416
- Ahiauзу, A. I. (2019). *The african thought system and the work behavior of the African industrial man :International Studies of Management and Organization*. Fashoyin. Nigeria: Macmillan Publishers
- Aluko, M. A.. O. (2013) Factors that Motivate the Nigerian Workers. *Journal of Ife Social Science Review*, Obafemi Awolowo University, Vol. 15, pp. 190–199.
- Anthony, K.A. (2014). Effect of workforce diversity on organizational performance of Selected Firms in Nigeria. *University of Nigeria*.
- Anu N. C. (2017) Impact of cultural differences on business performance of international organizations with special reference to Tech Mahindra and Honda. *International Journal For Innovative Research In Multidisciplinary Field* 3(2),54-63
- Baridam, D.M. & Nwibere, B.M. (2018). *Understanding and managing organizational behavior*. Port Harcourt: Sherbrooke Associates
- Benschop, Y. (2011). Pride, prejudice and performance: relations between, diversity and performance. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 12, 1166-1181
- Gitonga, D. W, Kamaara, M, & Orwar, G. (2016). Workforce diversity and the performance of telecommunication firms: the interactive effect of employee engagement (a conceptual framework). *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*. 6(6): 65-77.
- Tongo, N.I, Awomailo, L.B, Olufemi A. A. & Aderemi, T.A (2023). Impact of workplace diversity and inclusion on organisational productivity in Nigeria: A Case Study. *AUDOE* 4 (4) 57-75
- Truxillo, D. M., Cadiz, D. M., Rineer, J. R., Zaniboni, S., & Fraccaroli, F. (2012). A lifespan perspective on job design: Fitting the job and the worker to promote job satisfaction, engagement, and performance. *Organizational Psychology Review*, 2(4), 340–360.
- Tsui A.S. and Gutek, B.A. (2012) *Demographic differences in organization*, lexington books, New York.
- Ugwuzor, M (2014). workforce diversity management and corporate performance of firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management Review*.2,(4),36-46,
- Ukachukwu, C. C. and Iheriohanma, E. B. J (2013) The effect of cultural diversity on employee productivity in work organizations in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *International Journal of Development and Management Review* 8(1),1-15
- Umemezia, E. (2017) Culturally diverse workforce and performance in Nigerian public service: issues and challenges in people’s management context. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Management Research* 1(2); 23-33
- Vinnaras N., Ogunmola, G. A., Venkateswaran, .P. S. Rajest, .P. S. and Regin R. (2022) The impact of gender diversity on organizational performance in banks. *Turkish Journal of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation*; 32(3)1-10
- Warmate A. I., Zeb-Obipi, I. aqnd Jaja S. S. (2020) Cultural Diversity and Organizational Performance of 3 Star Hotels in South-South Nigeria *World Journal of Innovative* 9(4), 61-68.
- Warmate, Zeb-Obipi, and Jaja (2020) Gender diversity and organizational performance of 3 Star Hotels in South-South, Nigeria. *RSU Journal of Strategic and Internet Business* 5(2), 1164-1177
- Weiliang, E. C., Mun, L. S., Fong, T. S., & Yuan, Y. P. (2014). *The Effects of Workforce Diversity Towards the Employee Performance in an Organization*. University Tunku Abdul Rahman: Unpublished Thesis.
- Zahradeen, I. N. (2017) Impact of workforce diversity on organizational performance in Calabar, Cross-River State. The School of Business and Entrepreneurship, American University of Nigeria
- Zgourides, G. D., Johnson, I., & Watson, W. E. (2012). The influence of cultural diversity on leadership, group and performance: *An Examination of Learning Teams*, 3(5), 2-8.